

THE HISTORY OF LINGUISTIC TYPOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

What is linguistic typology? The term linguistic typology refers to studying, examining, classifying, or analyzing languages or concepts according to different types or categories. Before reviewing linguistic typology examples, it's important to really understand the definition of typology. Understanding what typology will make it easier to understand how certain examples illustrate the concept. A linguistic typology is simply a means of classifying items, people or concepts by general type. The word typology is simply a scientific term, which is used for grouping things together based on similarities. Linguistic typology can be used across all industries and disciplines. A few examples of fields in which typology is used include linguistics (as a linguistic typology or language typology), theology, anthropology, archaeology, psychology, politics, education, medicine, farming, and many others. In this article we shall look through the history of development of linguistic typology.

Introduction:

Typology is most often used to classify people, things or ideas into categories based on commonalities that they share.

Using typology helps researchers and others better understand certain conditions or factors by grouping things with similar characteristics together.

Typology is also beneficial and used in everyday life. Classifying similar things together provides a framework for processing, organizing and understanding information.

The word typology consists of two Greek morphemes: a) typos means type and b) logos means science or word. Typology is a branch of science which is typical to all sciences without any exception. In this respect their typological method is not limited with the sphere of one science. It has a universal rise. So, typology may be divided into:

1. Non-linguistic and
2. Linguistic typology

Non-linguistic typology is the subject matter of the sciences except linguistics and is also used in everyday life.

Linguistic typology is a new branch of general linguistics which studies the systems of languages by comparing, which looks for common laws of languages and finds out the differences and similarities between languages.

Main part:

Typology can be used in every field or industry, for that reason it's not surprising that there are many different typology examples. Some typologies are usually used by academic or professional researchers, but many others are used by ordinary people practicing their chosen profession or even in everyday life.

Linguistic typology has a rich history of development that cannot be studied without dividing into periods. So, each period has its own peculiarities as history itself. The prominent Uzbek linguist Dr. Buranov distinguished 4 main historical periods in linguistic typology.

The first period is characterized as spontaneous and evolutionary. It begins with the advent of first linguistic works, i.e. compiling separate grammars, on that time some linguists have already used ready-made models on the principle of analogy. During this period linguistic notions were studied within philosophy by Greek philosophers such as Aristotle. The works of philosophers are fundamental in the development of typology. As an example, we can say the following: Aristotle was one of the first of the ancient thinkers to approach the problem of grammatical form, developing the doctrine of the parts of speech as grammatical different classes of words. The main type of judgement, Aristotle considered the statement: "Noun – subject – noun – predicate". This period ended shortly before the Renaissance. On the basis of the ancient Greek linguistic heritage, the science of the language has emerged as an independent area and has been developed in other European countries.

The second period is characterized as the period of formation of linguistic comparison, when the first generalizing works in this area appear. The main works of this type include "Doctrinal" and "Por Royal Grammar". The "Doctrinal" or "The Manual for the Young" by Alexander of Villedieu known for its grammar, where word formation, syntax, metric and prosody of the Latin language were set out, and which was considered the most necessary book French, Italian and German schools for three centuries. The second biggest contribution to the subsequent development of the typology in Indo-European studies is the "Por Royal Grammar", which was published by Antoine Arnauld and Claude Lancelot in 1660 at the Por Royal Abbey near Paris. This work appeared as a result of the merging of the grammatical and philosophical ideas of that time. Philosophical thoughts were reflected in the identification of common units of the content side, while grammatical concepts formed the basis of the process of comparing multilingual units.

The third period of the linguistic typology history is connected with the development of comparative-historical linguistics, that is with the development of genealogical and typological classification of languages.

The fourth period is associated with the development of linguistic typology as an independent discipline. It coincides with the 20th century, the time of rapid extension of typological sciences on global scale, characterized by the division of linguistic typology into various specific areas, such as structural, genetic, areal, comparative typology. In the 20th century, a new stage of linguistic typology begins. This stage is tightly connected with the name of American linguist – E.Sepir. He created a fundamental new typology model based on

a set of general characteristics (types and ways of expressing grammatical concepts, the technique of combining morphemes, the degree of complexity of grammatical forms). The multi-character nature of this typology made it possible to build, instead of traditional 3-4 types, a more flexible and fractional classification reflecting the polytypologism of languages, diatypical variation, and the presence of transitional languages.

Conclusion:

In conclusion we can say that understanding typology is important if you are going to conduct a research or applied research. Typology is the systematic classification of objects or notions according to their common characteristics. It may refer to any field of science being characteristic of all branches of knowledge, because taxonomic description, classification and comparison of various objects are used both in linguistic and non-linguistic disciplines such as medicine, psychology, chemistry, biology, geography, sociology and etc. It's also beneficial if you wish to use different systems of classification in order to understand how things relate to each other. To get an understanding how typology used in many fields of study, think about various natural ecosystem examples. Each category is a typology. Any time you group things together, such as organizing words into different parts of speech, you're using a typology.

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